

Nonlinear Emergence of Creation

A stack of old, worn-out ideas can oft-suffice to occupy a leisurely afternoon of careful systematization of a man's creative output. Taking them one at a time, man then approaches each and its link with the next is forged in ink.

This procedure – replicated, adapted and varied – forms the backbone of much literary production in the present civil society. Some claim, however, that creativity and artistry lie beyond such a linear approach. Recall, however, that any curve can be broken into linear segments.

Thus, what we already have are the linear segments. We merely require an inclination or angle (which translates into “a viewpoint”) on the line segment. If the viewpoint is placed adjacent to the segment prior to concatenation, different storyboards can be woven from the same fundamental material.

This analogy may be carried further to all creation: simple, lawful productions coupled with observational colorings imparted by consciousness are stacked to generate the endless variations in creation.

Bibliography

1. Sri Aurobindo, The Life Divine
2. Karl Popper, The Logic of Scientific Discovery